

Cab Fare Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract-- The primary goal of the research article is to conduct a comparison of machine learning algorithms in order to estimate cab service fares. In this paper, the step is to develop a machine-learning model that can predict the cab fare considering a few factors. In today's world, many people depend on cab services that charge comparatively higher fares, and customers are forced to pay unwanted higher fares even though the prices are low. As a solution to this problem, a few machine learning techniques like Regression techniques such as Random Forest Regression have been used to implement this system.

Keywords — Machine Learning, Ensemble Learning, Regression Techniques, Random Forest Regressor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Regression models are developed using Machine learning algorithms. In this paper, the approach we used for the evaluation of the model has supervised learning since it is the best for predictive analysis. The data set constitutes the data collected from the past. Then the model training is done in order to handle new data. Based on this the output is predicted.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Previously, the only factor affecting the fare was the distance, but owing to technology improvements, the fare is now influenced by a number of factors, including the time of day, the location, the number of passengers, the amount of traffic, the number of hours, the base fare, and so on. The strategy is based on supervised learning, whose sole use in machine learning is prediction.

Banerjee, Pallab & Kumar [1] have discussed that numerous businesses, such as Uber, Ola, and others, use machine learning and artificial intelligence to solve the problem of accurate fare prediction.

Khandelwal [2] has done a study to examine the variables

that influence tariff divergence and how they relate to trade-related pricing differences. Uber and Ola take into account things like local traffic, demand, and supply variables.

Chao, and Junzhi [3] focused on the domains of economics, transportation, and operational studies, the patterns, and operations of the transportation system including the conventional tour technique that uses cabs and subways that are crucial study topics. And they arrived at results that could be instructional and helpful in practice by computing and assessing the impact of those factors on Uber riders' fare levels.

III. PURPOSE OF STUDY

In today's world, many people depend on cab services that charge comparatively higher fares, and customers are forced to pay unwanted higher fares even though the prices are low. This study is done to solve this problem. For this, we used different models to train the data set. The accuracy and error of the model using different algorithms are found. Based on this, the best regression algorithm chosen and is used to train and test the model.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research paper is about collecting the relevant dataset for training the machine learning models which predict the fare amount. Before modeling, data pre-processing has to be done. After that, the analysis of the data is done and a few visualization techniques are used to arrange the data in graphs and plots. Then, split the data set into test and train datasets. Here the machine learning techniques we used for the comparison and evaluation of these models are Random Forest regressor, Decision Tree regressor, and Linear regression. We use Google Colab in order to run python code easily and efficiently.

Google Colab

A product from Google Research called Google Colab is entirely cloud-based. Colab is a platform that makes it simple to run Python code and is ideal for algorithms, data analysis,

and machine learning. Technically speaking, Colab is a hosted service that requires no setup and is provided by a Jupyter notebook.

With Colab, you can explore and display data using the full power of well-known Python packages. You can input an image dataset into Colab, train an image classifier with it, and then look at the model.

Machine language

Machine learning is a method of data analysis that automates the creation of analytical models. Based on the idea that systems can learn from data, identify patterns, and draw conclusions with very little human input, it is connected to artificial intelligence. Machine learning has changed since its inception as a result of the development of new computing technologies. The assumption that machine learning is possible without being programmed for particular tasks and the pattern recognition methodology were the foundations for machine learning. The iterative nature of machine learning, in which data models freely adjust as they are exposed to new data, is its most crucial component.

Random Forest Regression

Random Forest Regression is a supervised learning algorithm that uses ensemble learning method for regression. A Random Forest outperforms a single decision tree in performance. It is used to tackle classification and regression problems and is also referred to as bagging. The fundamental concept is to integrate numerous decision trees to determine the outcome rather than relying solely on one. Random forests employ the decision tree bootstrap to lessen variation while preserving the decision tree model's low bias. The Random Forest approach for feature engineering can also be used to select the most crucial features from the features present in your training dataset.

The steps involved are:

Fig 1: Workflow

1. Dataset

The fare amount, the pickup longitude, the pickup latitude,

the drop-off longitude, the drop-off latitude, the distance, the surge multiplier, and the number of passengers were the eight columns of data that were utilized to collect data.[7]

fare_amount	pickup_longitude	pickup_latitude	dropoff_longitude	dropoff_latitude	passenger_count	distance	surge_multiplier
4.5	-73.844311	40.721319	-73.84161	40.712278	1	3.03	1
16.9	-74.016048	40.711303	-73.979268	40.782004	1	1.3	1
5.7	-73.982738	40.76127	-73.991242	40.750562	2	2.71	1
7.7	-73.98713	40.733143	-73.991567	40.758092	1	2.43	1
5.3	-73.968095	40.768008	-73.956655	40.783762	1	2.71	1
12.1	-74.000964	40.73163	-73.972892	40.758233	1	2.19	1
7.5	-73.980002	40.751662	-73.973802	40.764842	1	3.05	1
16.5	-73.9513	40.774138	-73.990095	40.751048	1	2.19	1

Fig 2: Dataset

2. Data Preprocessing

In machine learning, preprocessing the data is a crucial step in cleaning the data. Preprocessing makes clean data from raw data.

Handling Missing Data:

The mean strategy was used to fill in many missing data that existed before cleaning. During cleaning, the overall missing data are removed.

```

Train_Data.isnull().sum()

fare_amount      24
pickup_longitude 12
pickup_latitude  12
dropoff_longitude 10
dropoff_latitude  9
passenger_count  55
distance          0
surge_multiplier  0
dtype: int64
  
```

Fig 3: Before cleaning missing values

There are other approaches as well, such as median and mode, but mode can occasionally produce biased results. Mean and median are so preferred.

```

Train_Data.isnull().sum()

fare_amount      0
pickup_longitude  0
pickup_latitude  0
dropoff_longitude 0
dropoff_latitude 0
passenger_count  0
distance          0
surge_multiplier  0
dtype: int64
  
```

Fig 4: After cleaning missing values

3. Data Analysis

It is often referred to as an attribute selection in machine learning. The act of picking qualities involves choosing those that contribute the most to the desired attribute. The target attribute or prediction variable in this case is the fare amount, while the other qualities are independent variables. The

correlation matrix makes it easier to see how strongly the variables are correlated. The matrix indicates that each independent variable is significant for the prediction variable because they all influence it.

Finding the correlation between the different columns in a dataset gives:

Fig 5: Correlation Matrix

4. Split Data

The data set is split into test data and train data. After data analysis, training and test sets are created, and the Random Forest regressor method is executed.

```

08 ✓ from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
    # Divide the data into train and test
    train1,test1= train_test_split(Train_Data, test_size=0.2)
    
```

Fig 6: Splitting dataset

5. Build Model:

The random forest regressor has been trained, and we can now use it to predict certain things. We can assess our model using test data, and we use predict() to forecast the fare.

A. Random Forest Regression:

Random Forest Regression is a supervised learning algorithm that uses ensemble learning method for regression. Because it consists of multiple decision trees that work together to anticipate the goal value. The ensemble learning method combines predictions from various machine learning algorithms to provide more accurate predictions than those from a single model. A Random Forest outperforms a single decision tree in performance.[5] A group of trees provides a value that is more precise than one single tree.

```

45 ✓ #Random Forest
    from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
    RF_model = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators = 10).fit(train1.iloc[:, 1:7], train1.iloc[:,0])
    RF_model

    RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=10)

    RF_Predictions = RF_model.predict(test1.iloc[:, 1:7])
    
```

Fig 7: Random Forest Regressor

B. Linear Regression:

A predictive analysis methodology called a linear regression model applies analytical methods to a problem. It is the most well-known and straightforward machine-learning algorithm [7]. Between one or more independent variables (x) and a dependent variable(y), the method displays a linear relationship. The model identifies how the values of the dependent variable fluctuate as the value of the independent variable fluctuates since the algorithm demonstrates the linear relationship.

```

54 ✓ #Linear Regression
    values=["fare_amount", 'pickup_longitude', 'pickup_latitude', 'dropoff_longitude', 'dropoff_latitude', 'distance',
    linear_Data = Train_Data[values]
    cat_names = ['passenger_count']
    for i in cat_names:
        temp = pd.get_dummies(Train_Data[i], prefix= i)
        linear_Data = linear_Data.join(temp)

    predictions_LR = model.predict(test1.iloc[:,1:12])
    print("Predicted Fare:",predictions_LR[1])

    Predicted Fare: 9.723234873897546
    
```

Fig 8: Linear Regressor

6. Model Evaluation

The accuracy and error of the model trained using Random Forest Regressor and Linear Regressor are found separately.

```

38 ✓ predictions_LR = model.predict(test1.iloc[:,1:12])
    print("Accuracy and Error")
    MAPE(test1.iloc[:,0], predictions_LR)

    Accuracy and Error
    (51.14974957147028, 48.85025042852972)
    
```

Fig 9: Linear Regressor

The accuracy of the model using the Linear Regression algorithm is 51.14 and the error is 48.85.

```

08 ✓ print("Accuracy and Error")
    MAPE(test1.iloc[:,0], RF_Predictions)

    Accuracy and Error
    (75.13394956416963, 24.86605043583038)
    
```

Fig 10: Random Forest Regressor

And the accuracy of the model using the Random Forest Regression algorithm is 75.13 and the error is 24.86.

V. IMPLEMENTATION

The dataset is first loaded after which data within the dataset are trained and tested. Fare is predicted using random forest regression.

```
[406] #Random Forest
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestRegressor
RF_model = RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators = 10).fit(train1.iloc[:, 1:8], train1.iloc[:,0])
RF_model

RandomForestRegressor(n_estimators=10)
```

The output is generated after fitting the data into Random Forest Regressor algorithm.

```
[407] RF_Predictions = RF_model.predict(test1.iloc[:, 1:8])
print("Predicted Fare Amount=",RF_Predictions[6])

Predicted Fare Amount= 5.9799999999999999

[369] pickup_longitude=-73.97332001
pickup_latitude=40.76380539
dropoff_longitude=-73.98143005
dropoff_latitude=40.76380539
passenger_count=1
distance=2.32
surge_multiplier=1.75
output=RF_model.predict([[float(pickup_longitude),float(pickup_latitude),float(dropoff_longitude),float(dropoff_latitude),float(passenger_count),float(distance),float(surge_multiplier))])
print("Predicted Fare Amount:",output)

Predicted Fare Amount: [40.7443086]
```

Fig11: Random Forest Regressor

VI. CONCLUSION

The accuracy of the model using the Random Forest Regression is 75.13 and the error is 24.86 and the accuracy of the model using the Linear Regression is 51.14 and the error is 48.85.

Method	Accuracy	Error
Linear Regression	51.14	48.85
Random Forest Regression	75.13	24.86

Table 1: Comparison Table

We came to the conclusion that the Random Forest Regressor produces findings that are more accurate than those produced by the Linear Regressor. While linear regression assists in determining the linear relationship between the variables, Random Forest is effective for both classification and regression. As a result, we can say that Random Forest regression is the best and most effective technique for predicting fare.

VII. REFERENCES

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